

THE STUDY OF PHRASEOLOGY IN UZBEK LINGUISTICS

Yangiboyeva Kamola Iskandar qizi

Uzbek State World Languages University

Abstract:

This article offers the study of phraseological units in the Uzbek language.

Keywords: phraseology, phraseme, phrase, phraseology, phraseological dictionary.

Although the term “phraseology” is derived from the Greek word “phraseology” (phraseology – expression or speech), initially in Turkish Studies this term served to denote different meanings. For example, the 19th century Turkic scholar Mirza Kozimbek, based on the traditions of the time, used the word “phrase” in the meaning of “sentence” or “word” in his work, as in other figurative grammars written in Russian. When he says “phraseological compound”, he is referring to larger linguistic units than words. Giving information about verbs in Turkic languages, he explained such linguistic units as “compound verbs” as “grief” and also “emergence”. Phraseologism, phraseological unit, phraseology the general name of stable gardens, consisting of two or more words, spiritually equivalent to a related word combination or sentence, applied in a sense of integrity in a portable and indivisible. Phraseologisms, unlike syntactic structures that are similar in form, do not occur through the free choice or substitution of words in speech, perhaps it is applied as a pre-finished material with a meaning and a certain lexical grammatical composition, that is, it is impossible to extract, drop a part from the composition of phraseology: anqoning urug‘i, arpasini xom urmoq, o‘sha xarak - o‘sha darak, terisiga sig‘may ketmoq, kapalagi uchmoq, ko‘ngli joyiga tushmoq, qo‘li ochiq, qulog‘i og‘ir and others.

Although the term "phraseology" is derived from the Greek word “phrase” (phrasis-expression, speech wrapper), the term serves to express different meanings. For this reason, the term phraseology is used in linguistics in two senses: in the sense of the total number of phraseological units available in the language, and in the sense of the field of study of such units. So phraseology is the science of expressions. Like any other branch of linguistics, phraseology has its own stages of formation and development. In world linguistics, phraseology is one of the fastest growing areas of linguistics. In particular, the systematic study of phraseology in Turkic studies began in the 40s and 50s of the last century. During this period, significant progress was made in the study of grammatical, lexical and semantic units of phraseology in different languages. If phraseology is seen as a means of expression, it goes directly to Aristotle. As a linguistic fact, it was Ferdinand de Saussure who introduced it for the first time. The scientific study of the main problems of Uzbek phraseology began in the middle of the XIX century. Until the 1950s, phraseology did not form an independent branch of Uzbek linguistics.

LIST OF REFERENCES:

- 1) Kazimbek M.A. General grammar of the Turkish-Tatar language. Issue 2. Kazan. 1846.
- 2) Mamatov A. Boltaeva B. Semantic-pragmatic study of phraseological units. - Tashkent: Navruz. 2019.
- 3) National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan. - Tashkent: State Scientific Publishing House.
- 4) Rahmatullaev Sh. Some issues of Uzbek phraseology. - Tashkent: Fan.1966.
- 5) Vafoyeva M. Phraseological synonyms in the Uzbek language and their structural-semantic analysis. Filol.f.n. diss. abstracts. - Tashkent. 2009.
- 6) Bright M.H. Phraseological dictionary of Uzbek language. - Tehran: Khorasan Publishing House. 2013.
- 7) 7. Yuldashev B. Issues of Uzbek phraseology and phraseography. - Tashkent: Editor. 2013.
- 8) <http://google.uz/frazeolgiya/uz/094090>